

in treated seeds, showing that the fungus was internally borne, or at least present inside the seed coat.

Seedlings produced from the seed samples confirmed the presence of fungus in the vascular system. Bakanae symptoms appeared on plants grown to maturity.

Reisolation of the pathogen and back-inoculation to other rice plants confirmed its pathogenicity. □

Effect of grain discoloration in upland rice on some yield components

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The main causal agents of grain discoloration (GD) in upland rice in West Sumatra are different species of fungi, with *Helminthosporium oryzae* being the most important. Symptoms vary from spots invisible to the naked eye to a completely rotten endosperm. In susceptible varieties, the disease can cause complete yield loss.

We collected 50 panicles of susceptible upland rice variety Tondano in the Sitiung area and separated them into five groups, with disease severities of 1, 10, 30, 60, and 100%. Seeds of each severity

Rice seeds from different localities showing percent bakanae disease infection in Pakistan.

Locality	Seeds ^a showing <i>F. moniliforme</i> (%)		Seedlings showing <i>F. moniliforme</i> in vascular system (%)	Bakanae disease symptoms (%) in plants grown from untreated seeds
	Treated ^b	Untreated		
Amin Abad	9.5	6.2	10	6
Daska	6.0	1.5	6	7
G. G. Khan	0.0	0.0	0	0
Gujranwala	19.8	9.5	17	8
Hafiz Abad	11.0	7.2	12	7
Kala Shah Kaku	12.2	5.5	10	9
Narang Mandi	8.8	1.8	9	11
Sheikhupura	11.5	7.2	13	11
Sialkot	12.2	11.8	10	9

^aMean of 4 counts. ^bWith 0.1% mercuric chloride for 1 min.

group were planted in plastic trays (33 seeds/tray per replication) and grown in the greenhouse, to determine the effect of the disease on germination and plant height. Additional panicles of each severity group (3 panicles/replication) were used to study the effect of disease on grains/panicle. Weight of 100 grains was calculated for each severity group,

with three replications.

The higher the disease severity, the lower the germination and seedling height (see table). The disease reduced germination as much as 40% and reduced seedling height 3-20%. The higher the severity, the more the empty grains/panicle, with parallel weight reduction. □

Effect of rice grain discoloration on some yield components.^a

Severity of grain discoloration (%)	Germination ^b (%)	Seedling height ^c (cm)	Grains (no./panicle)				Weight of 100 grains ^e (g)	Reduction in weight (%10)
			Filled ^d	%	Empty	%		
1	92 a	10.9 (91) a	140 a	94	9 b	6	3.09 a	-
10	81 a	10.6 (86) a	137 a	90	16 b	10	2.94 a	5
30	80 bc	10.2 (79) a	135 a	91	14 b	9	2.95 a	4
60	73 c	9.7 (72) ab	101 b	74	35 a	26	2.56 b	17
100	52 d	8.7 (52) b	118 b	78	33 a	22	2.27 c	26

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not statistically different at a probability level of 0.05. ^bAv from 3 replications, 33 seeds/replication. ^cAv from 3 replications. Values in parentheses are total number of seedlings. ^dAv from 3 replications, 3 panicles/replication. ^eAv from 3 replications, 100 seeds/replication.

Integrated pest management—insects

Duration of diapause in white stem borer (SB) *Scirpophaga innotata*

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The white SB replaced the yellow SB *S. incertulas* in many parts of the northern coast of West Java in the 1989-90 wet season.

Replacement of improved Cisadane, a

135-d variety, with IR64 (110 d) lengthened the fallow period between dry and wet season crops to 3 mo. That favored the white SB, which can aestivate as prepupae at the base of rice stubble. The outbreak destroyed 15,000 ha of rice in the command area of the Jatiluhur Irrigation System (JIS) in Karawang, Subang, and Indramayu districts.

The JIS is divided into five regions of staggered water delivery. At Sukamandi, rice is transplanted ahead of that in Karawang. We collected aestivating prepupae from Karawang (52 d after

harvest) and Sukamandi (96 d after harvest) and subjected them to artificial rainfall and to flooding, to simulate land preparation for rice.

Frequency and amount of rainfall was based on the previous year's pattern. Water was poured onto prepupae in rice stubble placed in pots. Excised prepupae were placed individually in 12-cm-long, 0.5-cm-dim plastic drinking straws with cotton plugs in both ends. The straws were placed with the bottom cotton plug in contact with standing water, to simulate flooding.

Both watering methods terminated aestivation. The prepupae in the untreated

check remained in diapause. Aestivation ended sooner under artificial flooding than with artificial rainfall. Moths emerged 18-21 d after watering in the artificial flooding regime and 29-45 d after watering in the artificial rainfall regime (see table). □

Morphometric measurements of green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix nigropictus* (Stal) head and body during development

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We made morphometric measurements of the head and body of GLH during development of seven individuals. The results are in the table. □

Effect of artificial watering on diapause of white stem borer larvae, Sukamandi, 1990.

Simulated source of water	Observation	Source of prepupa ^a	
		Karawang	Sukamandi
Flooding	Prepupal duration	60 DAH	104 DAH
	Pupae transformed	5-8 DAW	4-8 DAW
	Moths emerged	18-21 DAW	18-21 DAW
Rainfall	Prepupal duration	52 DAH	96 DAH
	Moths emerged	29-45 DAW	29-45 DAW

^aDAH = days after harvest, DAW = days after watering.

Average length and width of the head and body of GLH at different stages.

	Head		Body	
	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Length (mm)	Width (mm)
1st nymphal instar	0.150 (0.131-0.171)	0.210	0.857 (0.802-0.921)	0.336 (0.315-0.368)
2d nymphal instar	0.215 (0.184-0.236)	0.236 (0.210-0.263)	1.088 (1.026-1.131)	0.381 (0.368-0.407)
3d nymphal instar	0.273 (0.236-0.302)	0.289 (0.263-0.315)	1.355 (1.289-1.394)	0.535 (0.486-0.578)
4th nymphal instar	0.457 (0.421-0.473)	0.557 (0.526-0.605)	2.849 (2.710-3.078)	1.041 (1.026-1.065)
5th nymphal instar	0.457	0.621 (0.578-0.657)	3.548 (3.342-3.684)	1.157 (1.078-1.210)
Adult male	0.342 (0.315-0.368)	0.731 (0.684-0.815)	3.981 (3.736-4.210)	1.390 (1.263-1.710)
Adult female	0.373 (0.342-0.394)	0.810 (0.763-0.842)	4.736 (4.473-4.868)	1.661 (1.526-1.894)

A new blister mite pest of rice in the Philippines

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Aceria saccharini (Acari: Eriophyidae), a blister mite pest of rice, has been reported on sugarcane in Indonesia; Australia; Taiwan, China; and India. It damages leaf sheaths and transmits streak virus disease. In 1988, it was reported to have transferred to rice in Sulawesi, Indonesia. Now it has been found in Central and Southern Luzon, Philippines.

Injury on rice is similar to that caused by thrips, and damage symptoms can be confused with tungro. Feeding produces white, chlorotic, shallow, gall-like pustules. Blisters vary in length (0.20-18 mm) and width (0.01-10 mm). The long proboscis of the mite probes vertically into the upper or lower epidermis of the leaf, lacerating tissues and rupturing both epidermal and parenchymous tissue cells.

Mites from different localities differ in color, from cream to pale yellow or

orange pink. The orange pink form is more prevalent. The adult mite is microscopic in size (0.16 ± 0.04 mm long, 0.05 ± 0.002 mm wide) (see figure). Mites moving on the leaf surface can be seen with the naked eye.

With magnification, the adults appear wormlike with a shield-shaped head. The body bears two pairs of slender legs anteriorly. All legs have claws, with 6-7 protruding feathered ray hairs each. The abdomen is annulated with 78-82 rings and three pairs of ventral setae. Eggs are spherical 0.05 mm in diameter, pale yellow turning to orange pink when about to hatch.

The pale yellow larva has a droplet-like shape with a large globular anterior, tapered posterior, and a pair of moderately long anterior legs. The protonymph, twice the size of larva, is whitish to light yellow with a thin layer of golden yellow hairs laterally. Both are orange pink when mature.

We monitored mite densities in 14 fields during the wet season. Three leaves each were sampled from the bottom,

A. saccharini adult (middle, 18×) transparent egg (right midlateral, 12×), and larva (bottom one-fifth, 18×).

middle, and top plant areas at seedling, maximum tillering, panicle initiation, and ripening stages. Ten samples per growth stage were bagged separately or placed in vials with 80% alcohol.